

MODERN ISSUES OF CONTRACT LAW IN AGRIBUSINESS

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Abstract: This article analyzes contemporary problems of contract law in the agribusiness sector. In particular, it covers uncertainties in the conclusion of contracts, the legal status of contracts in electronic form, the lack of legal advice and the consequences of violating the terms of the contract. The author puts forward solutions and proposals based on shortcomings in practice. In particular, initiatives such as creating an electronic contract platform, increasing legal literacy for farmers and entrepreneurs, and resolving disputes through mediation are proposed.

Keywords: agribusiness, contract law, electronic contract, legal advice, mediation, disputes.

Annotation: This article analyzes the modern problems of contract law in the field of agribusiness. In particular, it discusses uncertainties in contract drafting, the legal status of electronic contracts, lack of legal advice, and the consequences of contract violations. The author, based on practical shortcomings, proposes solutions and recommendations, including the creation of electronic contract platforms, improving the legal literacy of farmers and entrepreneurs, and promoting dispute resolution through mediation.

Keywords: agribusiness, contract law, electronic contract, legal advice, mediation, disputes.

Annotation: This article analyzes modern problems of contract law in the field of agribusiness. In particular, it examines uncertainties in drafting contracts, the legal status of electronic contracts, the lack of legal advice, and the consequences of breach of contract terms. Based on practical shortcomings, the author puts forward proposals and recommendations, including the creation of platforms for electronic contracts, increasing the legal literacy of farmers and entrepreneurs, and popularizing mediation for dispute resolution.

Keywords: agribusiness, agreement, electronic agreement, legal consultation, mediation, dispute.

INTRODUCTION. In today's globalization and digital economy, agribusiness has become one of the most important sectors of the economy. Indeed, as we know, humanity has a constant need for 3 things: food, clothing, housing, all of which cannot be provided without agricultural products. Regulation of legal relations in agribusiness, especially the correct and effective conduct of contractual relations, is one of the necessary conditions for the sustainable development of the industry. However, a number of problems arise in agribusiness contracts in modern conditions.

METHODOLOGY. Contracts in agribusiness usually cover various areas such as the supply of agricultural products, processing, storage, provision of services, or conducting partnership activities. These contracts are regulated by the Civil Code of the Republic of

Uzbekistan, the Law "On Farming" , the Law " On the Contractual Legal Framework of the Activities of Economic Entities " and other regulatory legal acts.

RESULTS. In practice, many contracts are concluded with general and vague expressions. This makes it difficult for the parties to clearly define their rights and obligations in the event of disputes. Each contract must be concluded taking into account its subject matter, parties, amount and other specific features, even taking into account possible disputes. Failure to comply with the form required by law will render the contract invalid only if it is directly provided for in the law.

A transaction whose content does not comply with the requirements of the legislation, as well as a transaction concluded with a purpose deliberately contrary to the principles of law and order or morality, is invalid in itself. The rules stipulated in Part Two of Article 114 of this Civil Code shall apply to such a transaction.

A transaction concluded in the presence of corruption, including a conflict of interest, will be declared invalid in court.

The legal status of electronic contracts is not fully established. Agribusiness entities often make technical and legal errors when concluding electronic contracts.

Some entrepreneurs and farms act without seeking legal advice when concluding contracts, which can be detrimental to them. Especially when concluding large contracts without legal advice, it can only worsen the situation of the business entity in the future.

Due to the frequent fluctuations in the prices of agricultural products, the terms and conditions at the time of conclusion of the contract quickly become irrelevant. This necessitates the adaptation of the legal mechanisms of the contract.

There are cases of violation of the principles of injustice and proportionality in determining penalties and compensation in case of breach of contract. When drawing up a contract, it is necessary to individualize it when using model contracts or copying from other contracts . Failure to do so may lead to various misunderstandings.

Solutions and suggestions:

- Develop methodological guidelines for concluding contracts with clear and complete terms.
- Creating electronic contract platforms for agribusiness entities and providing them with legal guarantees.
- Organizing seminars and trainings to increase the legal literacy of farmers and entrepreneurs.
- Including special clauses in contracts that take into account financial risks such as inflation and price fluctuations.
- Introduce proportionate and fair liability mechanisms for breach of contract terms.

It is also a wise initiative to popularize the use of mediation in resolving disputes between parties to a contract. This will save them time and money, and if a mediation agreement is concluded before the judge leaves the courtroom (consultation room), the case will be dismissed based on Article 122 of the Criminal Procedure Code and Article 107 of the Criminal Procedure Code, and the state fee will be refunded.

Furthermore, if the contracts are notarized and registered with the state, it will be possible to collect the debt through a notary's writ of execution.

CONCLUSION. The development of contract law in the agribusiness sector on a solid and modern basis not only regulates interpersonal relations, but also ensures trust and stability in the entire industry. Therefore, timely identification of modern problems and their elimination with legal solutions is one of the main directions of protecting the interests of agribusiness entities.

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